

Neuroprotective Effect of *Centella Asiatica* Leaf Alkaloid Extract on Enzymes Linked with Aluminium-Induced Alzheimer's Disease in *Drosophila Melanogaster*

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18165880>

Abstract

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder that is linked with loss of cholinergic neurons in the brain and a reduction in the level of the neurotransmitter, Acetylcholine. The main therapeutic target in the treatment of AD is the inhibition of Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) in the brain. This study investigated the neuroprotective effect of dietary inclusion of *Centella asiatica* leaf alkaloid extract on enzymes linked with Aluminium-induced Alzheimer's disease in the fruit flies, *Drosophila melanogaster*. Alkaloid extract was prepared by extraction method and 10 mg/ml of the extract was used for the experiment. Flies were induced with Alzheimer's disease by adding 40 mM of Aluminium chloride (AlCl₃) to their diet. Thereafter, flies were treated with alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaf for seven days. The mortality record of the flies was taken daily, locomotor performance of flies was measured on Day 7 after which the flies were homogenized and assayed for activities of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE). Results showed there was no significant difference (P<0.05) in the survival rate and locomotor performance of induced flies treated with the extract and induced flies treated with the standard drug, Donepezil, when compared with the control. Also, activities of the enzymes (AChE and BChE) linked with Alzheimer's disease were reduced significantly (P<0.05) in the group treated with the extract and in the group treated with Donepezil, when compared to the control. This study therefore suggests that alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaf have neuroprotective effect on the enzymes linked with aluminium-induced Alzheimer's disease in *D. melanogaster*.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease, *Drosophila melanogaster*, *Centella asiatica*, Dietary supplementation, Acetylcholinesterase, Butyrylcholinesterase.

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder which is linked to the loss of cholinergic neurons in the brain as well as the decreased level of the neurotransmitter, Acetylcholine (Nigel *et al.*, 2005). AD represents the most common form of dementia (Alzheimer's Disease Facts and Figures, 2022), significantly affecting people's daily life, especially the population over the age of 65, with problems such as neuron death, memory loss, cognitive disorders, and cholinergic dysfunction (Yıldırım and Güzeldemirci, 2023). Other symptoms that characterize AD include inability to perform everyday activities, depression, anxiety, behavioral changes, poor judgment, impaired communication and difficulty in walking. (Alzheimer's Association, 2021). It is estimated that over 50 million people suffer from some form of dementia worldwide and this figure is expected to increase to 139 million by 2050. (GBD Neurology Collaborators, 2016; WHO, 2022).

The major pathological characteristics of brains affected with AD include neurofibrillary tangles, loss of neurons, the presence of senile plaques mainly composed of beta-amyloid peptide, tau protein phosphorylation, oxidative stress, neuroinflammation and low levels of acetylcholine (ACh) neurotransmitter in the hippocampal and cortical region of the brain (Gauthier *et al.*, 2021; Bhagat *et al.*, 2021; Bortolami *et al.*, 2021; Carcak-Yilmaz *et al.*, 2017; El-Khatibi *et al.*, 2021; Nguyen *et al.*, 2021). The main therapeutic target in the treatment of AD is the inhibition of Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) in the brain (Savelev *et al.*, 2004). However, current available AD medications namely Donepezil, Rivastigmine, Galantamine and Memantine (Hyde *et al.*, 2013), are unable to stop the disease progression but can only reduce its symptoms (Nguyen *et al.*, 2021). The side effects of drugs as well as high cost associated with the treatment (Anand and Singh, 2013; Tayeb *et al.*, 2012), has prompted the search for a more holistic approach with natural source and less cost for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

Medicinal plants have been used all over the world as natural sources of medicines (Saranya *et al.*, 2017). *Centella asiatica* (L), commonly known as Indian Pennywort and Gotu Kola, is one of the important medicinal plants used around the world (Sakshi *et al.*, 2010; Saranya *et al.*, 2017). It is used as a medicinal herb in Ayurvedic medicine, Western Herbal Medicine, traditional African medicine, traditional Chinese medicine and in western orthodox medicine. The medicinal properties of the plants are mainly due to the presence of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, saponins, reducing compounds, minerals and vitamins (Vinoth *et al.*, 2011; Latif *et al.*, 2019).

In literature, *C. asiatica* has been reported to have various neuroprotective effects such as rejuvenant, anxiolytic, sedative and intelligence promoting property, on the central nervous system and related ailments (Kumar and Gupta, 2002). Due to its diverse biological components and actions, *C. asiatica* is well known and has been used for centuries for a number of medical problems including cognitive disorders (Gohil *et al.*, 2010; Orhan, 2012).

The fruit fly, *Drosophila Melanogaster* is used as a genetic model for numerous human diseases including the neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's, Huntington's, Spinocerebellar ataxia, Alzheimer's, oxidative stress and diabetes (Lenz *et al.*, 2013). Though several animal models have been used in order to understand and find new and more effective treatments for neurodegenerative diseases (Giannakou and Crowther, 2011), knowledge of the anatomy, brain and nervous system of *D. Melanogaster* as well as its genetic, behavioral, methodological and economic advantages along with its short life span, make the fruit fly a leading model for research

(Prüßing *et al.*, 2013). In addition, the worldwide drift from the use of animal models to the use of insect models for experimental studies due to ethical issues such as animal care and preservation of animals has brought about the use of *D. melanogaster* model in this current research.

Despite the great therapeutic potential of alkaloids for the treatment of AD, it may be concluded that investigative research particularly those related to the alkaloids of *C. asiatica* seems to be highly neglected (Abbas *et al.*, 2019). The dual effect of centella leaf alkaloid extract on AChE and BChE in a fly model of AD is also not fully explored. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the effect of dietary inclusion of alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaf on enzymes linked (AChE and BChE) with Alzheimer's disease in wild Oregon strain of *Drosophila melanogaster*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Material

Fresh leaves of *Centella asiatica* were collected from New Era Farm, Ile Oluji, Oke-Igbo Local Government Area, Ondo State, Nigeria. Authentication was carried out at the Department of Crop, Soil and Pest Management, The Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria.

Reagents and Materials

All the chemical reagents used for this study were of analytical grade, obtained from Sigma Al-drich, Co. (St. Louis, Missouri, USA) and the water used was glass distilled.

Preparation of Alkaloid Extract from *Centella asiatica* Leaves

The freshly collected leaves were thoroughly rinsed under running tap water, sun-dried, and ground into a fine powder. Alkaloid extract of the sample was prepared according to the method of Harborne (1998), with slight modifications. 50g of the powdered leaves was soaked in 150ml of ethanol and acetic acid solution (9:1 v/v) in an air tight container and placed on an orbital shake. The mixture was then filtered using a muslin cloth followed by filter paper (Whatman No. 1). The filtrate was allowed to air-dry for five days after which the dried extract was stored in a refrigerator until required for use.

Culturing of *Drosophila melanogaster*

The cultivation of *Drosophila melanogaster* was carried out with slight adjustments following the method outlined by Hosamani & Muralidhara, 2009. The wild Oregon strain of *Drosophila melanogaster* was sourced from the Drosophila Laboratory at The Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA), Ondo State, Nigeria. These flies were raised and kept in the fly laboratory under standard conditions, specifically at 22±°C with 70-80% relative humidity. The fly diet was prepared using the procedure by Farombi *et al.*, 2018, with minor modifications. The diet consisted of 0.85L of water, 52g of cornmeal, 5g of yeast, 7.9g of agar agar, 1g of methyl parabene/nipagene (as a preservative), and 1ml of absolute ethanol. In brief, the initial portion of water (0.7L) was brought to a boil in a pot, while the remaining water (0.15L) was used to dissolve the cornmeal, and the yeast was dissolved in a small amount of hot water. Agar agar was added to the boiling water with continuous stirring and allowed to boil for 10 minutes. The dissolved cornmeal was then added to the boiling water with stirring and cooked for another 10 minutes, with occasional stirring, before the dissolved yeast was incorporated. The cornmeal mixture was cooked for an additional 15 minutes with occasional stirring before being removed from the heat. A nipagene-ethanol mixture, prepared by dissolving nipagene in 1ml of absolute ethanol, was

thoroughly mixed into the cornmeal after it had cooled. The prepared cornmeal was then distributed into glass vials, into which the flies were introduced.

Experimental Model

The experimental setup followed the method outlined by Oboh *et al.*, 2018, with slight adjustments. In summary, Alzheimer's disease was induced in the flies using 40 mM of AlCl₃. Adult male and female flies, aged 3 to 5 days, were divided into five groups, each containing 40 flies, as detailed below:

Group A - Flies received a basal diet and 1 ml of distilled water, totaling 5 g.

Group B - Flies were given a basal diet and 1 ml of 40 mM AlCl₃, totaling 5 g.

Group C - Flies were provided with a basal diet and 1 ml of 40 mM AlCl₃ plus 1 ml of 10.0 mg/ml *Centella asiatica* extract, totaling 5 g.

Group D - Flies were fed a basal diet and 1 ml of 10.0 mg/ml *Centella asiatica* extract, totaling 5 g.

Group E - Flies were given a basal diet and 1 ml of 40 mM AlCl₃ plus 1 ml of 20 µM Donepezil, totaling 5 g.

The flies underwent these treatments for a duration of 7 days in glass vials at room temperature. All experiments were conducted in triplicate. The concentration of aluminum chloride (AlCl₃) used was selected based on a prior study on aluminum toxicity in *D. melanogaster* (Wu *et al.*, 2012).

Lethality Response

The flies were observed every day to track mortality, and the count of deceased flies was documented daily for each group. The collected data were analyzed and presented as cumulative mortality and the percentage of surviving flies.

Measurement of the Locomotor Performance using Negative Geotaxis Assay

After 7 days of treatment, the locomotor performance of flies in different groups was evaluated using the Negative Geotaxis Assay, as outlined by Bland *et al.* (2009) with minor adjustments. The surviving flies from each group were anesthetized on ice and placed in separate labeled sterilized tubes (11 cm in length and 3.5 cm in diameter), which were then sealed. After a 10-minute recovery period, the tubes were tapped at the bottom, and the number of flies that crossed the 6 cm mark within 6 seconds was recorded. The results were expressed as the percentage of flies that moved beyond a minimum distance of 6 cm in 6 seconds. Subsequently, the average climbing performance was calculated.

Preparation of Tissue Homogenates

Tissue homogenates of the flies were prepared following the method by Farombi *et al.*, 2018, with slight modifications. The surviving flies from the various treatment groups were anesthetized on ice, weighed, and homogenized in Eppendorf tubes with 0.1 M phosphate buffer at pH 7.0 (1/10 w/v) using a Teflon homogenizer. The supernatants were obtained by centrifuging the homogenates for 10 minutes at 10,000 X g and 4°C in a Kenxin refrigerated centrifuge Model KX3400C (KENXIN Intl. Co., Hong Kong). The resulting supernatants were separated from the pellets and transferred into labeled Eppendorf tubes for use in various biochemical assays.

Determination of Total Protein

The total protein content of fly homogenates was determined using the Coomassie blue method, as described by Bradford (1976), with 1 mg/ml serum albumin as the standard. A mixture of 10 µL of fly homogenates, 250 µL of Coomassie blue, and 20 µL of distilled water was prepared. The reaction mixture was incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes, after which the absorbance was measured at 595 nm using a spectrophotometer. The total protein content was then calculated.

Determination of Acetylcholinesterase Activity

The activity of acetylcholinesterase in the tissue homogenate was measured using a modified version of Ellman's colorimetric method (Perry *et al.*, 2000). The assessment of AChE activity involved a reaction mixture that included 200 µL of fly tissue homogenate in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer at pH 8.0, 100 µL of a 3.3 mM solution of 5,5'-dithio-bis (2-nitrobenzoic) acid (DTNB) in a 0.1 M phosphate buffered solution at pH 7.0 with 6 mM NaHCO₆, varying amounts of alkaloid extracts (0–100 µL), and 500 µL of phosphate buffer at pH 8.0. Following a 20-minute incubation at 25 °C, the reaction was initiated by adding the AChE substrate, which was 100 µL of a 0.05 mM solution of acetylthiocholine iodide. The absorbance of the mixture was then recorded every 15 seconds over a 5-minute period at 412 nm using a spectrophotometer. The activity of AChE was calculated and reported as µmol AChE/h/mg protein.

Determination of Butyrylcholinesterase Activity

The tissue homogenate butyrylcholinesterase activity was assessed according to a modified colorimetric method of Ellman (Perry *et al.*, 2000). BChE activity was determined in a reaction mixture containing 200 µL of fly tissue homogenate in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 8.0), 100 µL of 3.3 mM solution of 5,5'-dithio-bis (2-nitrobenzoic) acid (DTNB) in 0.1 M phosphate buffered solution (pH 7.0) containing 6 mM NaHCO₆, alkaloid extracts (0–100 µL) and 500 µL of phosphate buffer (pH 8.0). After incubation for 20 minutes at 25 °C, the reaction was subsequently initiated by adding BChE substrate (100 µL of 0.05 mM solution of butyrylthiocholine iodide). The absorbance of the mixture was monitored for 5 minutes (15 seconds interval) at 412 nm in a spectrophotometer. Thereafter, BChE activity was calculated and expressed as µmol BChE/h/mg protein.

Statistical Analysis

The results of replicate readings were obtained and expressed as mean ± standard deviation (S.D) values, data for three replicate analysis was subjected to statistical evaluation with the use of the software Graph pad PRISM (V.5.0). The obtained results were statistically analyzed using the One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's Multiple Comparison Test. The significance difference was accepted at $p \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Figure 1, the survival rate (%) of Alzheimer's disease induced flies and treated flies is shown. The result shows that there was a significant reduction in the survival rate of induced flies (81.9%). When compared with the control, there was no significant decline ($P < 0.05$) in the survival rate of induced flies treated with alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaves (92.5%), induced flies treated with the standard drug (93%), Donepezil and normal flies fed with the extract (93%). This shows that the extract as well as the standard drug were able to improve the rate of survival of flies induced with Alzheimer's disease.

The values of locomotor performance (%) of Alzheimer's disease induced and treated *Drosophila melanogaster* is shown in Figure 2. When compared with the control group, the climbing behavior of induced flies significantly declined while the climbing behavior of normal flies fed with the extract significantly increased. There was no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the locomotor performance of induced flies treated with the extract and that of the induced flies treated with the standard drug, Donepezil when compared with the control. The percentages of flies that went across the 6cm mark within 6 seconds were 80% for flies in the control group; 42.8% for flies induced with aluminium; 78.7% for induced flies fed with diet containing extract, 98.7% for normal flies fed with diet containing extract alone and 76.2% for induced flies fed with diet containing the standard drug, Donepezil.

Figure 3 shows the AChE activity after 7 days of treatment for *Drosophila melanogaster* used in the experiment. When compared to the control group ($P < 0.05$), there was a significant difference in the AChE activity of induced flies as the AChE level greatly increased. The AChE activities of induced flies fed with diet containing extract, normal flies fed with extract and induced flies fed with diet containing Donepezil were not different significantly from the AChE activity of flies in the control group ($P < 0.05$).

Presented in Figure 4 is the BChE activity of treated and induced flies used in the experiment. There was significant change in the BChE activity of induced flies upon comparison with the control group ($P < 0.05$) as the BChE level greatly increased. The BChE activities of induced flies fed with diet containing extract, normal flies fed with extract and induced flies fed with diet containing the standard drug, Donepezil were not different significantly from the BChE activity of flies in the control group ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 1: Survival rate (%) of *Drosophila melanogaster* used for the experimental model. Values represent mean \pm Standard Deviation (n=40).

KEY:

Group A = Control

Group B = Aluminium induced flies fed with normal corn meal diet

Group C = Aluminium induced flies fed with diet containing 10.0mg/ml of alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaves

Group D = Normal flies fed with diet containing 10.0mg/ml of alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaves

Group E = Aluminium induced flies with 20 μ M Standard drug, Donepezil included in their diet

Figure 2: Percentage locomotor performance (Negative Geotaxis) of *Drosophila melanogaster* used for the experimental model. Values represent mean \pm Standard Deviation (n=40).

KEY:

Group A = Control

Group B = Aluminium induced flies fed with normal corn meal diet

Group C = Aluminium induced flies fed with diet containing 10.0mg/ml of alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaves

Group D = Normal flies fed with diet containing 10.0mg/ml of alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaves

Group E = Aluminium induced flies with 20µM standard drug, Donepezil included in their diet

Figure 3: Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity in *Drosophila melanogaster* used for the experimental model. Values represent mean ± Standard Deviation (n=40).

KEY:

Group A = Control

Group B = Aluminium induced flies fed with normal corn meal diet

Group C = Aluminium induced flies fed with diet containing 10.0mg/ml of alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaves

Group D = Normal flies fed with diet containing 10.0mg/ml of alkaloid extract of *Centella asiatica* leaves

Group E = Aluminium induced flies with 20µM standard drug, donepezil included in their diet

Figure 4: Butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) activity in *Drosophila melanogaster* used for the experimental model. Values represent mean \pm Standard Deviation (n=40).

KEY:

Group A = Control

Group B = Aluminium induced flies fed with normal corn meal diet

Group C = Aluminium induced flies fed with diet containing 10.0mg/ml of alkaloid extract of Centella asiatica leaves

Group D = Normal flies fed with diet containing 10.0mg/ml of alkaloid extract of Centella asiatica leaves

Group E = Aluminium induced flies with 20µM standard drug, Donepezil included in their diet

This present study investigated the neuroprotective effect of *Centella asiatica* leaf alkaloid extract on enzymes linked with Alzheimer's disease (acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase) in *Drosophila melanogaster*. Vital findings of this study are that post-Aluminium treatment of *D. melanogaster* with *C. asiatica* leaf alkaloid extract improved survival rates as well as locomotor performances and decreased the activities of the two cholinesterases, acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) in the flies.

Heavy metal toxicity is one of the major causes of Alzheimer's disease (AD). Various heavy metals like aluminium, cadmium, lead, iron, aluminum, etc. have been constantly linked to Alzheimer's disease. Aluminum toxicity has been linked to oxidative stress which has an established relation

with neurodegeneration. Several studies have also revealed elevated levels of aluminum in the brain of patients experiencing memory deficit (Choudhury *et al.*, 2023). Numerous studies involving the linkage between aluminum and Alzheimer's disease have been performed which have suggested the effectiveness of aluminum in inducing the disease (Mahdi *et al.*, 2019).

Administration of aluminium to the *Drosophila melanogaster* in this study could have been responsible for the loss and death of cholinergic neurons, which led to the reduced rate of survival as well as poor locomotor performances reported in the flies. However, treatment of the induced flies with *Centella asiatica* alkaloid leaf extract improved the survival rate and the locomotor performance of the flies, confirming the neuroprotective effect of the extract. In addition, there was no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the survival rate and locomotor performance of flies in the group treated with the extract when compared to the control and the group treated with the standard drug, Donepezil. This also proves that the extract was not toxic to the flies at the 10 mg/ml used in this study.

Alkaloids are a diverse group of naturally occurring organic compounds that contain at least one nitrogen atom. Qualitative screening of phytochemicals in the leaves of *C. asiatica* show that alkaloids are present in the plant (Saranya *et al.*, 2017). Liquid chromatography - mass spectrometry (LC-MS) analyses of *C. asiatica* extract by Ondeko *et al.*, 2020, also confirm the presence of alkaloids in the plant. Alkaloids exert neuroprotective effects by inhibiting cholinesterase activity and apoptosis, decreasing oxidative stress, ameliorating neuroinflammation and modulating autophagy (Ali *et al.*, 2023). This support the neuroprotective effect of the extract shown in this study.

The pathology of how Alzheimer's disease arises is complex. However, the most accepted theory for AD is the cholinergic hypothesis. Acetylcholine (ACh), an important neurotransmitter, is vital for both the central nervous system (CNS) and autonomous nervous system. ACh is responsible for both memory and learning tasks in the brain by providing communication between two nerve cells. During neurotransmission, ACh is released from the nerve into the synaptic cleft and binds to ACh receptors (nicotinic and muscarinic) on the post-synaptic membrane, relaying the signal from the nerve. ACh is the biomarker in AD (Yıldırım and Güzeldemirci, 2023).

Cholinesterases are esterases that break down choline-based esters, most of which serve as neurotransmitters. They catalyze the hydrolysis of these cholinergic neurotransmitters such as breaking acetylcholine into choline and acetic acid. These reactions are vital to allow a cholinergic neuron to return to its resting state after activation. There are two types of cholinesterase, namely acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) (Dorland, 2014). AChE which is located on the post-synaptic membrane, plays a major role in the regulation of acetylcholine when it terminates the signal transmission by hydrolyzing ACh to choline and acetate. AChE activity increases in AD brain, thus triggering the degradation of acetylcholine (Bhagat *et al.*, 2021; Design, 2021). Hence, inhibition of AChE activity reduces the breakdown of acetylcholine. BChE, the isoenzyme of acetylcholinesterase, is a minor element in the brain of a healthy person. The activity of BChE is increased due to plaque and tangles in the brain of patients with AD. Therefore impaired cholinergic transmission can also be treated by inhibition of BChE (Li *et al.*, 2018; Weinreb *et al.*, 2012).

Based on the cholinergic hypothesis in AD pathology, inhibition of the activities of cholinesterases with the use of cholinesterase inhibitors (ChEI), which attempt to block acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase enzymes, is the most effective approach in AD treatment. This tries to restore

ACh levels by increasing them at cholinergic synapses, thereby making up for cholinergic losses and increasing cholinergic transmission (Alptüzün *et al.*, 2006; Bhagat *et al.*, 2021; João *et al.*, 2021; Miles *et al.*, 2021).

Most research conducted on ChE activity usually focus on assessing and inhibiting the activity of AChE alone. However, this current research focused on assessing and inhibiting the dual effect of both AChE and BChE in Alzheimer's disease. From the results shown in this research, administration of aluminium on the flies increased activities of the both AChE and BChE. However, treatment with *Centella asiatica* alkaloid leaf extract inhibited and reduced the activities of both AChE and BChE in *D. melanogaster* flies induced with Alzheimer's disease. In addition, there was no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the AChE and BChE activities of flies in the group treated with the extract when compared to the control. Flies treated with the extract also appeared to show better levels of acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase activities when compared to the flies treated with the standard drug, Donepezil.

The reduction in AChE and BChE activities in the flies used for this study could have brought about increased ACh levels, as well as restored cholinergic losses and increased cholinergic transmission in the flies, as reported in this study. This corroborates the findings from a previous study by Rahman *et al.*, 2012, where the ethanolic extract of *C. asiatica* was tested for anti-AChE activity in-vitro and the results confirmed that it possessed a significant level of anti-AChE activity.

CONCLUSION

This present study shows that alkaloid extract of *C. asiatica* leaf reduced the rate of mortality and improved locomotor performance in flies induced with Alzheimer's disease, using aluminium. The extract also inhibited activities of the cholinesterases AChE and BChE, thereby reducing the loss of cholinergic neurons. Therefore, it may be concluded that *C. asiatica* leaf alkaloid extract have neuroprotective effect on the enzymes (acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase) linked with aluminium-induced Alzheimer's disease in *D. melanogaster*.

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